

A Physics-Informed Neural Network as a Digital Twin of Optically Turbid Media

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In this article, a novel methodology for characterizing and creating a digital twin of turbid media with intensity measurements only is presented, employing a unique physics-informed neural network approach. Unlike previous approaches utilizing various deep neural network architectures that often function as black boxes, the method prioritizes interpretability, offering a clearer understanding of the underlying processes of light propagation through turbid media and estimating the transmission matrix. The possibility and use case of gradient calculation through this presented digital twin are showcased by solving the problem to retrieve the initial wavefront shape of the light that passed through the medium (e.g., the image transmission problem). The results surpassed the accuracy of models directly optimized for this task, underscoring the precision of the proposed digital twin. This capability represents a pivotal advancement for future developments in neuromorphic and deep learning computation and training using such a photonic and optical systems.

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, extensive research has been dedicated to unravelling the complex relationship between input and output light fields of a multimode optical fiber (MMF).^[1–11] When coherent light is injected into an MMF, it couples with multiple guided

modes, leading to complex interference patterns at the output facet. This phenomenon, known as speckle patterns, poses challenges for image transmission through MMFs, as variations at the input facet strongly impact the entire speckle pattern at the output. Interferometric techniques have revolutionized imaging across these turbid media, enabling the measurement of their transmission matrix (TM) and a set of novel applications, including a new generation of optical endoscopes based on single MMFs.^[12,13]

Traditionally, measuring the complex valued TM of an optical fiber assumes the preservation of coherence properties during the scattering process and requires an interferometric measurement of transmitted light typically made via off-axis holography with an external refer-

ence.^[6,14,15] Achieving stability in the interferometer, especially over long optical paths, is crucial. Alternatives like phase-stepping holography with a co-propagating internal reference field have emerged to address stability concerns.^[16–18] However, due to phase discontinuities within the internal reference, “blind spots” appear within the output field of view of the fiber.^[16–18]

Recently, convolutional neural networks (CNNs)^[19–26] and vision transformers^[27–30] have been employed to address the constraints associated with interferometric measurements. Noteworthy studies showcase the efficacy of these techniques in tasks such as image transmission, wavefront shaping, and holography at the distal end of MMFs. However, a common limitation in most of these methods is the opaque nature of the deep neural network’s actual performance. It acts as a black box, offering limited insights into how precisely these methods translate speckle patterns into the input electric field of the turbid media. Typically, these techniques work on recognizing features in the input–output relation and are thus unable to transmit unfeatured datasets and thus underutilize the capacity of the MMF.

An alternative approach has recently emerged for characterizing the MMF fiber, employing a physics-informed neural network (PINN).^[31] In this innovative method, a single-layer complex-valued neural network (CVNN) has been implemented to map the modulated phase, facilitated by the spatial light modulator (SLM), onto the amplitude of the recorded polarized light originating from the proximal facet of the fiber. The versatility of this technique is demonstrated through its cascading capability,

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allowing the creation of a multilayer CVNN for describing stacks of multiple turbid media. However, to fully harness this method for digital twinning purposes, an extension to all propagating polarizations of light is essential. Importantly, advancements in the field of deep physical neural networks and optical neural computation rely on having a digital twin with the capability of gradient calculation for the training of these systems.^[32–34] Another significant challenge associated with the utilization of PINN is the prerequisite for being unstructured to have an accurate knowledge of the governing equation dictating light transmission through the media and its modulating elements. This task proves to be particularly formidable due to the inherently highly nonlinear transformation introduced by modulating elements employed to control the input light field, such as the SLM. MMF also scrambles the polarization of the light^[15] as the electromagnetic wave propagating in such a guiding medium. Even with meticulous calibration and modulation, their capabilities remain confined to the modulation of only one polarization of light. This limitation introduces additional nonlinearity, especially in the presence of other optical components like polarizers within the system. Thus, the intricate interplay of these elements further complicates the already challenging task of precisely characterizing and controlling light transmission through the media.

In this study, we propose a PINN able to estimate how light propagates through a turbid MMF. Such architecture not only characterizes the scattering media to indirectly deduce the TM for all polarizations but also provides a sufficiently descriptive understanding of the fiber's physics. This understanding extends to the point where the network can indirectly contribute to the complex task of image transmission through turbid media of unknown nonlinear modulation, thus serving as a digital twin of the physical system.

The proposed method boasts substantial advantages over deep learning-based approaches. First, it is not a black box; its performance is grounded in the physics of light propagation in MMFs, allowing for direct association of all optimized weights and biases in the network with physical properties of the system. The possibility and use case of gradient calculation through this presented digital twin are showcased by solving the reverse problem, finding the input modulation pattern that leads to a specific speckle pattern, therefore retrieving the initial wavefront shape of the light that passed through this medium. In solving this image transmission problem, our model surpassed models directly optimized for this task, underscoring the level of accuracy and generality achieved by this digital twin. Indeed traditional deep learning-based methods often rely on data's features, limiting their generalization. For instance, a model developed for handwritten digit images may struggle to generalize effectively to reconstruct images from other datasets, such as those containing natural scenes.^[21,25] In contrast, the digital twin solution for image reconstruction works based on pixel reconstruction, leading to context-free, universal image reconstruction. This distinctive feature enhances the adaptability and broader applicability of our method. Finally, this digital twin concept enables the utilization of our method for a variety of tasks, particularly in calculating gradients for training neuromorphic photonic and optical systems.^[32]

2. Methodology

2.1. Optical System

The optical setup employed in this study is detailed in **Figure 1a,b**, comprising three telescopic systems, a half-wave plate (HWP), a phase-only SLM, two reflecting flat mirrors, a beam splitter, an MMF (step index MMF, core diameter 50 μm , numerical aperture $\text{NA} = 0.22$, and two microscope objectives (MO) (MO1: 0.65 NA, 40 \times , AMEP4625, ThermoFisher) and (MO2: 0.65 NA, 40 \times , RMS40X, Olympus), each coupled with a CCD camera. For laser light coupling into the SLM screen, lenses denoted as L1 and L2 are positioned in a 4f configuration. The reflected light from the SLM is then guided into the first MO (MO1), effectively conjugating the SLM screen onto the back aperture of MO1. Monitoring the proximal side involves CCD1 and a telescope setup (L4 and MO1). The generated speckle, along with the distal side of the fiber, is recorded using CCD2, facilitated by a telescopic arrangement (MO2 and L5).

To optimize coupling efficiency while ensuring effective mode excitation, we selected an MO with a numerical aperture (NA) higher than that of the fiber. This choice allows for the excitation of all fiber modes, though it naturally limits the coupling efficiency of pixels from the SLM into the fiber. To address this, we experimentally determined the optimal coupling region on the SLM and used only a subsection of the SLM screen (256 \times 256 pixels) rather than the entire 512 \times 512 pixel area, maximizing alignment and coupling efficiency. Throughout this setup, the SLM pattern is precisely commanded, and the resulting speckle pattern is recorded using a computer.

2.2. Physical Formalism of the Optical Setup

Taking into account the relatively low power of the continuous laser utilized in this study (<100 mW), we can treat the entire system as a linear time-invariant system. Consequently, by applying the superposition principle, we can articulate the behavior of the electric field vector at the output facet of the MMF in response to the modulated phase from the SLM as

$$\mathbf{E}(x, y) = \sum_{w=1}^W \mathbf{U}_w(x, y) e^{j\phi_w} + \mathbf{Z}(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where $\vec{\mathbf{E}}$ denotes the electric field vector, while $\vec{\mathbf{U}}_w$ represents a complex vector corresponding to the electric field at the distal ends of the fiber, resulting from light emitted from a single pixel on the SLM screen. The Neper number is denoted by e , ϕ_w represents the modulated phase from the same SLM pixel, and W the number of SLM pixels. Additionally, $\vec{\mathbf{Z}}$ characterizes the electric field caused by unmodulated light from the SLM. Finally, x and y specify the spatial location on the distal side of the MMF in the Cartesian system (see **Figure 1b**).

Nevertheless, due to the camera's inherent limitation in recording electric field components or phase, our observations are confined to values proportional to the electric field's

Figure 1. a) The utilized optical setup and b) a schematic illustrating the tangential electric field vector on the distal facet of the fiber, along with the selected Cartesian coordinate systems for the speckle patterns and the polarization of the electric field, denoted by the axes pairs (x, y) and (a, b) , respectively. c) An example of the utilized dataset in this study along with their corresponding speckle patterns. d) PCA transformation of the speckle patterns used in this study. Facial images are obtained from CelebA^[35] dataset.

amplitude. Consequently, we formulate the camera reading as follows:

$$|E|^2(x, y) = E_a^2(x, y) + E_b^2(x, y) = \sum_k^{a, b} \left| \left(\sum_{w=1}^W U_{k,w}(x, y) e^{j\phi_w} + Z_k(x, y) \right) \right|^2 \quad (2)$$

In this context, we introduce subscripts a and b , to signify components within an orthogonal Cartesian system established at the distal facet of the fiber. It's crucial to highlight that this Cartesian system may not align with the previously defined coordinates $(x$ and $y)$ for the distal fiber facet (see Figure 1b). In this formulation of the electric field intensity, there is no strict requirement for these coordinate systems to align.

In a more general case of the both phase and amplitude modulation, we can formulate the electric field intensity as follows:

$$|E|^2(x, y) = \sum_k^{a, b} \left| \left(\sum_{w=1}^W U_{k,w}(x, y) (f_r(\phi_w) + jf_i(\phi_w)) + Z_k(x, y) \right) \right|^2 \quad (3)$$

In this expression, the real functions f_r and f_i represent the real and imaginary components of the modulation. It is essential to note that in this generalized scenario, ϕ_w does not exclusively define the phase modulation; rather, it serves as a more comprehensive modulation parameter. This broader form of modulation will be employed later on for training the digital twin of the optical system. Notably, in this training process, we seek to discover the nonlinear complex modulation, which remains unknown.

2.3. Data

By systematically transmitting multiple images through this turbid media, we construct an extensive dataset composed by the amplitude $|\vec{E}|$ of the speckle patterns and the phase of the modulation parameter (ϕ_w) . In this context, our objective is to ascertain the unknown complex variables $U_{k,w}$, Z_k , and the real modulation functions, f_r and f_i , in case of dealing with unknown modulation. For this study, we acquired a set of 150 000 SLM patterns and their associated speckle patterns. This collection comprises 120 000 randomly generated SLM patterns,

10 000 patterns showcasing celebrity faces from the CelebA dataset,^[35] 10 000 patterns of handwritten digits from the MNIST dataset, and finally, 10 000 patterns from the CIFAR dataset. Each grayscale image was employed to modulate light using the SLM, introducing phase shifts ranging from 0 to π . The corresponding speckle patterns resulting from these modulations were recorded by CCD2.

Figure 1c displays examples of images from each dataset along with their corresponding speckle patterns. Additionally, we conducted principal component analysis (PCA) and uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP), Figure 1d, on the speckle data to visualize the distribution of this dataset. The PCA and UMAP projections unequivocally reveal significant distinctions in the statistical characteristics of speckle patterns from each dataset. The clear separation observed in both PCA and UMAP projections emphasizes the distinct and discernible nature of speckle patterns originating from the various datasets. One objective of this study is to demonstrate that the physics-informed model, once trained on one dataset, can be applied universally to other datasets, despite clear statistical differences between them. This is a challenge that conventional deep learning models cannot easily address, as their performance is restricted to the learned features from their training dataset, resulting in limited generalization capabilities.^[24] We have also utilized the data presented in ref. [21] to showcase the usability of the method for unknown modulation and different optical configuration.

3. Results and Discussion

In the following, we present a PINN to implement Equation (2) and (3) through its architecture. The network learns the physical properties of the MMF and of the employed optical system, generating all the parameters to create a digital twin of the turbid medium. The derived twin is then applied to solve the inverse problem of image transmission through MMFs.

3.1. Neural Network Architecture

Our proposed approach grounds on the neural network elucidated in Figure 2a. The network is designed to accept one input which is the phase mask of the SLM ϕ_w (dashed red block), accompanied by a tensor operation emulating Equation (2) (dark gray box). This is complemented by a cost function assessing the similarity between the generated speckle by the neural network and the ground truth, quantified through mean absolute error (MAE).

To understand the utilized tensor operations, we should first notice that it is not necessary to investigate the entire (x, y) plane of the output facet of the fiber.^[25,31] Instead, we can reduce the problem by considering only H selected points in that space. This matter does not affect the generality of the problem as H can be taken large enough to cover all the pixels of the recording camera.

Therefore, by considering this selection, Equation (2) can be transformed into a set of H nonlinear equations. This can be

Figure 2. a) Schematic of the utilized physics-informed neural network architecture. The trainable variables are marked with dashed blue squares, and the nonlinear complex transformation of modulation for the case of known modulation is depicted inside the red square. Blue tensors are real number valued, while orange ones represent complex number tensors. b) A simple architecture of a one-input and one-output deep neural network model that generates the real or imaginary part of the modulation. c) A 1D deep convolutional neural network that applies a similar transformation as in (b) across all input values.

done by determining both variables with spatial dependencies ($U_{k,w}(x, y)$ and $Z_k(x, y)$) at H points. As $U_{k,w}(x, y)$ variable has modulation element dependency in its subscript, we can represent these complex values in a 3D array with the size (W, H, s) . W covers the modulation parameter; H covers the sampled points from speckle. Finally the last element of the triplet is defined to accommodate the real and imaginary part of $U_{k,w}(x, y)$ ($s = 1$ or $s = 2$). In contrast, for $Z_k(x, y)$, we only have spatial dependency so a tensor with size of $(1, H, 2)$ suffices for its full description.

Moving forward, for the input, the modulated real-valued phase ϕ_w is reshaped into a tensor of size $(1, W, 1)$ and subjected to a complex element-wise operation denoted as e^{jT} , where T represents the elements of the replicated tensor. Please note that this has been done for the case of the known phase only modulation. Importantly, the output of this operation is a complex-valued tensor of the modulated phase. Then, we multiply the resulted tensor to additional variable tensor (A) with the same shape $(1, W, 1)$. The reason behind the definition of this additional tensor is that if a pixel of the SLM is not contributing in the speckle generation (i.e., weak optical coupling such as being out of the accepted NA of any of the utilized optical elements), the corresponding number in that variable tensor can turn into zero. This effectively weights the computed U_k against the efficiency of the optical setup. In principle, it is possible to skip this step; however, this would result in a loss of information as an entire column of U_k would need to be discarded. Practically we found that addition of this tensor can not only prove helpful in the training process but also can deliver an insightful understanding of the optical system coupling behavior. This will be discussed in details in the following sections.

The resulted complex-valued tensor of the phase modulation is then subjected to matrix multiplication with the complex-valued version of U_k tensor. Following this multiplication, the complex-valued tensor is taking the shape of $(1, H, 1)$. The tensor is then added to the unmodulated part, complex-valued tensor (Z_k), followed by the calculation of the absolute value and powering to two, as indicated in Equation (2). This whole operation, except the part for the phase and its correction, needs to be repeated for all instances of “ k ” to produce two tensors at the output, namely V_a and V_b . Based on Equation (2), then the summation of these two can be equated to the selected pixel’s values from speckle. The MAE loss finds the difference between the calculated speckle value and the actual measured one.

The presented model can also be applied to create an accurate digital twin of the optical system even when the modulation is not a pure phase modulation. This happens for instance when both phase and intensity of the input beam are modulated or when the effects of the modulating element on intensity and phase are unknown or unclear (hereafter referred to as unknown modulation). Through the following method, this complex-valued unknown modulation can be discovered during the training process. To achieve this, we implement the mathematical model of the optical setup described in Equation (3). Instead of relying on the function e^{jT} used for phase-only modulation, we employ a nonlinear activated deep neural network. This neural network, illustrated in Figure 2b as a single-input single-output model, consists of two hidden layers with 20 nodes each,

utilizing exponential linear unit activation functions. The output node is activated with a hyperbolic tangent function. The selection of these activation functions ensures that the neural network model mimics a continuous and derivable function at all points. It is important to note that two versions of this neural network are required to produce the two independent real-valued functions f_r and f_i as per Equation (3). Another crucial consideration is that these neural network functions must be applied to the entire modulation element. Therefore, we propose implementing these functions as a form of multilayer 1D CNN, as illustrated in Figure 2c. This implementation, equivalent to Figure 2b, ensures that the same function is applied to all modulating parameters. We implemented the neural network using TensorFlow in Python. For optimization, we used the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.001 for 100 epochs.

During the training the variables Z_k , U_k , and A_k are estimated. Such trained network can be employed to emulate how light propagate through the MMF, obtaining an high-fidelity speckle pattern for a given input modulation, as described in Section 3.1. The high-fidelity speckle retrieval grounds on the fact that each of the trained variable has a specific physical meaning, depicted in Section 3.2: U_k represents a numerical polarization-dependent TM that can digitally twin the MMF from which the training dataset has been constructed, Z_k models the unmodulated light transmitted through the fiber, while A_k gathers the efficiency at which the different pixels of the modulating element are coupled into the MMF. This intimate link between the network and the physics of light propagation through the optical system enables efficient trainings (Section 3.3) and to use the exact same model to reconstruct the wavefront that generate a specific speckle pattern, even in a condition in which the modulation applied to the input beam is not fully known (Section 3.4).

3.2. Digital-Twin of the Turbid MMF

The primary function of this trained physics-informed model is to predict the speckle pattern based on the given SLM input. This capability is showcased across all testing datasets in Figure 3 and 4, where both 10 000 and 1024 sampling points from the speckle are analyzed.

In these figures, Figure 3a,b, and 4a,b illustrate the reconstruction of sampled speckle patterns and their disparities from the ground truth for SLM inputs derived from randomly generated images, CIFAR, celebrity faces, and MNIST, respectively. The associated reconstruction errors are graphically represented in Figure 3e1 and 4e1. Notably, the model exhibits superior performance with randomly generated images but faces more challenges with the MNIST dataset.

Moreover, Figure 3, 4 provide UMAP projections of the sampled speckle from the MNIST dataset, with each projected speckle colored according to the handwritten digit it represents. Remarkably, both the ground truth (Figure 3 and 4e2) and the reconstructed speckle (Figure 3 and 4e3) exhibit very similar topology and clustering of handwritten digits. This suggests that the reconstructed sampled speckle effectively captures the patterns and features of the MNIST dataset.

This promising outcome underscores the potential for reverse transformation using the trained model. In the next sections, we

Figure 3. a–d) Examples of speckle pattern reconstruction for randomly generated images, CIFAR, celebrity faces, and MNIST, respectively. This reconstruction was performed using only 10 000 points of the speckle, and the plotted patterns are interpolated by the nearest neighbor method to produce an image. e1) MAE of the reconstructed speckle pattern. e2,e3) UMAP of the ground truth speckle and the reconstructed one, respectively. Facial images are obtained from the CelebA dataset, which contains celebrity images.^[35]

will employ the model to predict the SLM pattern required to generate a given speckle pattern. Unlike previous deep learning models, this approach stands out as we leverage the physical equations of the fiber to address this problem.

3.3. Physical Meaning of Trained Variables and Discovery of the Unknown Modulation

The depiction of all 1024 randomly selected points from speckle, alongside the optimized A for both cases of phase-only and unknown modulation functions, can be observed in

Figure 5a–c, respectively. As previously mentioned, the A tensor adopts a shape of $(1, W, 1)$, where W denotes the number of modulated pixels on the SLM screen. Consequently, A can be reshaped to match the SLM screen shape for visualization purposes.

The A tensor exhibits almost identical shapes when the same training dataset is applied to the phase-only network (Figure 2a) or the unknown modulation network (network in Figure 2b applied to the network in Figure 2a), with the sole difference lying in their amplitudes—a point we will delve into later. Additionally, the NA of the MMF is mirrored in this tensor as a circular curve at the top of the reshaped A tensor, reflecting

Figure 4. a–d) Examples of speckle pattern reconstruction for randomly generated images, CIFAR, celebrity faces, and MNIST, respectively. This reconstruction was performed using only 1024 points of the speckle, and the plotted patterns are interpolated by the nearest neighbor method to produce an image. e1) MAE of the reconstructed speckle pattern. e2,e3) UMAP (uniform manifold approximation and projection) of the ground truth speckle and the reconstructed one, respectively. Facial images are obtained from the CelebA dataset, which contains celebrity images.^[35]

the relative angular alignment between the SLM screen and the fiber. It is understood that all SLM pixels falling outside the accepted NA of the fiber would result in very weak optical coupling into the fiber, thus playing a less significant role in speckle generation compared to those with better coupling (and therefore having a very low value in the A tensor).

Figure 5d–f demonstrates the unknown modulation (decomposed in f_r and f_i) uncovered by the designed convolutional network. It is crucial to note that while this discovered modulation may deviate from the theoretical one, it does so solely through a linear mapping. This is evident from Equation (3), where substituting $f_r + jf_i$ with $L(f_r + jf_i) + B$, where B and L are complex-

valued numbers, maintains the equation's structure. In Figure 5e, by setting L to $0.019 - 0.1j$ and B to $0.48 - 2.11j$, the discovered non-linear modulation aligns with the theoretical prediction. Here, the artificial intelligence (AI)-discovered modulation is depicted in orange, while the theoretical modulation and the linearly scaled AI-discovered modulation are represented in blue and red, respectively. Similarly, Figure 5f presents the same dataset in a 3D axis, where the third dimension corresponds to the modulation parameter, a scalar number ranging from 0 to π .

Together with the coupling efficiency, the proposed method retrieves the polarization dependent TM. Figure 6a1,a2 shows

Figure 5. a) Location of the randomly selected sampling points on the speckle. b,c) Extracted tensor A for the cases of known and unknown modulation. d) Discovered real (f_r) and imaginary parts (f_i) of the nonlinear modulation. e) Linearly scaled version of the discovered transformation and its comparison to the ground truth. f) Same result as e) with the modulation parameter also shown across the third dimension.

representative data of the absolute value of discovered tensors U_a and U_b . In these figures, the x axis is indicating the SLM pixel index while vertical axis shows the sampled point index from the speckle side. A representative matrix to analyze these sensors is the cosine similarity (CS).

$$CS_k = \hat{U}_k \cdot \hat{U}_k^\dagger \quad (4)$$

In this analysis, \hat{U}_k represents the normalized U_k tensor, where all rows have an amplitude equal to one, while \hat{U}_k^\dagger denotes the complex conjugate transpose of \hat{U}_k . Figure 6b1,b2 displays the absolute value of the calculated CS, CS_a , and CS_b , with a closer examination provided in the zoomed versions (Figure 6c1,c2).

The CS plot is characterized by the presence of parallel lines, particularly noticeable adjacent to the main diagonal elements. Remarkably, these lines are spaced at intervals of 32, indicating a relationship between pixels from the upper and lower rows of the SLM. This suggests that neighboring pixels on the SLM screen exhibit similarity in their TM rows, as illustrated in Figure 6b1,b2 with the zoomed versions in Figure 6c1,c2, respectively. To further elucidate this phenomenon, we can extract a row from the CS matrix and reshape it back to match the SLM screen shape, as demonstrated in Figure 6d1 for the 500th row of Figure 6b1. Evidently, pixels close to the selected pixel display similar TM rows, whereas the similarity diminishes as we move further away. This observation cannot be attributed to the selected dataset alone, as there is no correlation between randomly generated pixel data. Instead, it stems from the underlying physics of the optical system, indicating that spatially close

pixels on the SLM exhibit similar physical characteristics and effects in speckle generation.

Another interesting observation arises when calculating the CS) of each row in Figure 6a1 to the corresponding row in Figure 6a2. This yields 1024 values, each indicating the similarity between the governing equations for different polarizations. It is important to note that Figure 6a1,a2 depicts the TM for perpendicular polarizations of light at the speckle side. These 1024 values can then be reshaped to match the SLM screen shape and visualized as depicted in Figure 6d2. As already mentioned, each pixel of the SLM is coupled into the fiber at a different angle: pixels located at the center of the NA are coupled perpendicularly to the distal fiber's facet axis, while pixels farther away are inserted at an angle. Figure 6d2 illustrates that when the insertion angle is perpendicular to the distal fiber facet, the output speckles are polarized, evident from the strong CS in the center of this figure (red color). Similarly, as the insertion angle increases (i.e., moving away from the center of the NA), the similarity between the two polarization transmission matrices decreases, resulting in polarization loss. This observation aligns well with the physics of the fiber, as perpendicular insertion angles lead to strong coupling of lower-order modes that maintain polarization better.

3.4. Exploring Data Requirements and Training Dynamics

To gauge the optimal data requirements for training the presented physics-informed model effectively, we conducted a series of experiments utilizing datasets of varying sizes.

Figure 6. a1,a2) The discovered transmission matrices for two perpendicular polarizations. b1,b2) Absolute values of the cosine similarity matrices of a1,a2), respectively. c1,c2) Zoomed versions of b1) and b2), respectively. d1) Reshaped version of the 500th row of b1). d2) Absolute value of the cosine similarity of the same row from a1) to a2) reshaped back to the SLM's shape. e1,e2) Learning curves illustrating the network's performance as it's trained with various dataset sizes. The vertical axis represents the dataset size, while the horizontal axis denotes the epoch number.

Initially, the model underwent training using 100 000 pairs of input–output data, with 20 000 pairs reserved for validation. This training employed a batch size of 128, resulting in 782 steps per epoch. Subsequently, we systematically reduced the dataset size by increments of 5000 data points for each subsequent experiment. Concurrently, we adjusted the batch size to ensure a consistent number of training steps across different dataset sizes. For example, when the dataset comprised only 5000 data points, we set the batch size to 6, thereby maintaining equitable training conditions across all dataset sizes. Throughout all experiments, validation was consistently performed on the same set of 20 000 pairs of data, ensuring uniform evaluation across different dataset sizes. Figure 6e1,e2 depicts the loss and validation loss curves observed across all dataset sizes over the course of 100 training epochs. Analysis of these curves reveals that dataset sizes smaller than 10 000 points often led to instances of overfitting, characterized by a declining loss curve coupled with a steady increase or plateauing of the validation loss. Notably, achieving a validation MAE loss of 9.4 typically required ≈ 70 000 data points and around 70 epochs of training. However, the model could attain a validation MAE loss of 11 with as few as 15 000–20 000 data points within just 20 training epochs. This

underscores the model's capacity to effectively operate with a minimal dataset, enabling it to grasp the intricacies of light modulation and extract polarization-dependent transmission matrices.

It is important to note the consistency in training time across different dataset sizes, with each epoch requiring ≈ 5 s. This uniformity is attributed to the maintenance of an identical number of training steps per epoch irrespective of the dataset size (by changing the batch size). Consequently, the process of characterizing the optical system through the physics-informed calculation can be completed in as little as 35 s for datasets comprising 100 000 data points, and up to 95 s for smaller datasets containing 15 000 points.

3.5. Universal Pixel-Wise Image Transmission through the Fiber

As discussed previously, the presented digital twin of the optical system offers a significant advantage: the ability to compute gradients of its output, enabling various applications. One such application is image transmission through the fiber. For this task, we propose utilizing the neural network depicted in

Figure 7. a) Schematic of the model utilized for the image transmission task. b) Schematic of the developed regularization technique. c) An example of the reconstructed image of various datasets when only 1024 sampled points of the speckle have been used for the physics-informed model (when only one polarization is considered in the network architecture). This plot displays both image reconstruction and its corresponding spatial error when the proposed regularization has not been used (R/without) and the reconstruction when the proposed regularization has been used (R/with). d) Same result as c) but when the physics-informed model considers both possible polarization (see Figure 2). e1–e3) Image reconstruction fidelity in terms of MAE and structural similarity index (SSIM) for all the developed models for the MNIST, CIFAR, and celebrity faces datasets, respectively. f) Image reconstruction comparison when one or two light polarization of speckle have been considered for the network training. Facial images are obtained from the CelebA dataset, which contains celebrity images.^[35]

Figure 7a. This model comprises two elements. First, a single-layer fully connected layer, consisting only of weights without biases, is connected to a constant input. The output of this layer is activated using a sigmoid activation function multiplied by the constant π . This ensures that the output of each node in the layer falls within the range of zero to π . This step aims to find the SLM pattern corresponding to the given speckle. Second, the output of this single layer is connected to the previously trained physics-informed model (e.g., the one in Figure 2), which translates

the given SLM pattern from the previous layer into speckle patterns (forward model). To prevent changes in the weights and biases of the physics-informed model during training, the model is frozen.

With the entire model being drivable, gradient-based optimization to calculate the SLM pattern can be applied (through the single layer at the beginning) to produce a specific given speckle pattern (through the physics-informed model). However, this approach often leads to overfitting, posing a significant

challenge. Although the physics-informed model accurately translates MNIST, CIFAR, or face images into their respective speckle patterns with an MAE loss exceeding 20, overfitting the single layer can yield a substantially lower loss, thereby producing inaccurate results. To address this issue, we introduce a regularization method depicted in Figure 7b. Leveraging the fact that the reconstructed image is stored in the weights of the single layer (due to the absence of biases), these weights can be extracted and reshaped into the expected image. Human-perceivable images exhibit grid topology and a sense of locality, meaning nearby pixels have higher correlation than those farther apart. Additionally, in addition to randomly generated data, images tend to be smooth, with variations in pixel values between adjacent pixels typically not strong. This concept is operationalized through a kernel (weights) regularized for the layer, where the spatial differences of the image in both horizontal and vertical directions are calculated. These differences are represented as e_1 and e_2 in Figure 7b and utilized to introduce an additional loss term during training, comprising weighted sums of the mean and square of these values. This combination forms a Lasso regularization, which should make sharp changes sparse in the resulting image, while the ridge (sum of squares) decreases the value of the differences.

In addition to the introduced regularization, we have benchmarked the effect of incorporating both polarizations in the calculation of the TM through our physics-informed model. It should be noted that the single-polarization TM can be obtained by a slight modification in the architecture of the physics-informed model depicted in Figure 2, by only considering $k = a$ in Figure 2. This result is depicted in Figure 7c,d for single and double polarization for representative images, and quantitatively evaluated Figure 7e in terms of MAE and structural similarity index (SSIM). Considering two polarizations achieves better results compared to single polarization when regularization is not considered. When considering the mentioned regularization the model with two polarizations exhibits the best reconstruction fidelity. The MAE error distribution for the CIFAR dataset is depicted for both cases of single and double polarization when regularization has been applied in Figure 7f. It is evident that the double polarization model exhibits better image reconstruction, particularly in the corners of the images where the need for more than one polarization TM is expected (refer to data presented in Figure 6d2).

An interesting observation is a weaker reconstruction of the MNIST as compared to other dataset used in this study. Since our method performs pixel-wise reconstruction, the difficulty of reconstructing any dataset should theoretically be similar. However, the images in the MNIST dataset are highly structured, with distinct regions of phase shift within the handwritten digits and zero phase shift in the background areas. This structure leads to higher reconstruction loss due to the contrast between the non-shifted background and the shifted pixels of the digits.^[25] Essentially, the noise in the reconstruction has a more pronounced effect in regions with sharp transitions, such as the boundaries of the digits.

However, despite the higher reconstruction loss observed for MNIST, the resulting images are still quite readable to the human eye. This is due to the simplicity of the dataset, where the basic structure of the digits makes it easier for a human

to interpret the reconstructed images, even if the reconstruction loss is higher.

It's important to note that this physics-informed model is solely trained on randomly generated images, showcasing the universality of the image transmission model and its independence from dataset context.

3.6. Analysis of Sampling Points and Image Reconstruction

In our digital twin framework (SLM to speckle transformation), each sampled point of the speckle image is reconstructed independently, using separate rows from the Z_k , U_k , and A tensors (see Figure 2). This independent optimization suggests that varying the number of sampled points does not significantly impact the performance of the digital twin model itself, which transforms the SLM pattern into sampled speckle values. This has been confirmed experimentally, as shown in Figure 8a, where the minimum validation loss remains stable across different numbers of sampled points.

For the image reconstruction task (speckle to SLM transformation), however, the scenario differs. Here, we aim to estimate 1024 independent SLM pixel values from the sampled speckle data. In mathematical terms, we solve for the 1024 SLM pixels using m nonlinear equations, where m represents the number of sampled points and must be at least equal to the number of independent SLM pixels. This requirement is demonstrated in Figure 8b, where the SSIM of reconstructed images increases with the number of sampled points up to about 1000 points when no regularization is applied. The slight SSIM increase beyond 1000 points reflects additional regularization from the overdetermined system and associated noise.

Interestingly, when applying our proposed regularization, the reconstruction fidelity improves even when fewer than 1024 sampled points are used. This improvement occurs because the regularization leverages the locality and redundancy in human-perceivable images, allowing for higher SSIM even with a reduced sampling rate.

3.7. Application of PINN to a Different Setup

To assess the proposed method in a different optical configuration, we utilized data from ref. [21], obtained through a 1 m long step-index fiber with a core size of 105 μm , capable of carrying ≈ 9000 optical modes, using a 532 nm wavelength continuous laser. Image intensity was coupled in to the MMF using a polarizing beam splitter, an HWP, and an MO. The resulting speckle was captured using a 4f configuration and a digital camera.

The methodology introduced by Caramazza et al. demonstrated for the first time the possibility to apply a neural network to retrieve transmitted natural images through an MMF. The approach involves a complex matrix correlating the image amplitude (square root of the intensity) at the two ends of the fiber, hence provided data are amplitude based. This is evident from the sorted unique values of the pixels in the recorded speckle, as illustrated in Figure 9a (in blue). The pattern formed by these blue values indicates the square root nonlinear transformation over the data. However, when we calculate the square of the provided amplitude data and examine the sorted unique values, a

Figure 8. a) Validation loss versus the number of sampled speckle points in training, showing minimal impact on the digital twin model's performance across different sample sizes. b) SSIM of reconstructed SLM patterns as a function of the number of sampled points used. Without regularization, SSIM increases steadily with more sampling points up to around 1000 (black vertical line), after which improvements taper off.

Figure 9. The discovered complex modulation and transmission matrices, along with their cosine similarity matrices, for the dataset used in the study by Caramazza et al.^[21] employing our proposed method. a) Sorted unique speckle values in amplitude (blue) show a square root non-linearity, while their squared values (orange) form a linear intensity distribution. b) Discovered A tensor, indicating lower coupling efficiencies at SLM edges. c) Real (blue) and imaginary (orange) parts of the modulation functions. d) Complex modulation with real and imaginary components. e1, e2) Transmission matrices for both polarizations. f1–h2) Cosine similarity matrices and reshaped views, revealing SLM pixel correlations and grid topology with 92-pixel periodicity.

Figure 10. An example of image reconstruction using the proposed method for the testing dataset utilized in the study by Caramazza et al.^[21] A comparison with ComplexNet, developed by Caramazza et al. is also presented in the form of a bar chart.

straight line is formed (in orange), corresponding to intensity recording of the camera. This analysis is important to apply our PINN to Caramazza et al data, since our methodology requires speckle in intensity rather than amplitude (see Figure 2).

We tested whether our PINN for an unknown modulation (network in Figure 2b applied to the network in Figure 2a) can find the appropriate nonlinear mapping during model training and retrieve the training variables U , Z , and A with the related physical meanings. For training, we randomly selected 10 000 samples from the speckle due to the higher number of modes that this optical setup can accommodate. Training was conducted over 100 epochs on their training dataset (45 000 natural science images from the ImageNet dataset), while testing was exclusively performed on their testing set (motion images in the Mybridge dataset).

Figure 9b depicts the discovered A tensor in the proposed algorithm. Similar to our example, this graph indicates lower coupling efficiencies due to the NA of the optical components, as the SLM pixels at the corners of the screen represent weaker coupling. Figure 9c shows the real and imaginary parts of the modulation in blue and orange (discovered f_r and f_i functions), respectively, with the modulation parameter on the x axis. Figure 9d displays complex modulation, with the real and imaginary parts of the modulation on the horizontal and vertical axes, respectively, while the color of each point represents the modulation parameter.

Figure 9e1,e2 represents the TM for both polarizations, and similar to our optical setup, their CS matrices are calculated and represented in Figure 9f1,f2, with a zoomed version in Figure 9g1,g2, respectively. As in the previous case, parallel lines appearing in the CS matrix are due to the grid topology of the SLM, with the distance between lines now being 92 pixels, indicating the use of 92×92 pixel images in their experiment.

The reshaped versions of the 4000th row of the CS matrix to SLM screen shape for Figure 9f1,f2 are also presented in Figure 9h1,h2, respectively. Similar to our setup, this demonstrates correlations of nearby SLM pixels and effective perpendicularity between the effects of the pixels located far apart on the SLM screen.

We have employed the discovered variables to test the developed physics-informed model for this optical setup in the intricate task of image transmission. The results and their comparison to the original article are illustrated in **Figure 10** with representative images and quantitative comparison, showcasing higher structural similarity SSIM for the physics-informed approach. We believe that this can be attributed to the fact that our trained model is able to retrieve the physical properties of the optical system. These discovered parameters by our PINN are obtained with no prior knowledge about the optical system and modulation type of ref. [21].

4. Conclusion

In this study, we have introduced a physics-informed approach to digitally twin optically turbid media. As example system, we chose to work with MMFs, in which turbidity is mostly introduced by modal interference and dispersion. The neural network is constructed in such a way to replicate the general equation governing the input–output relation, and the training procedure designed to retrieve unknown variables linked to the physical properties of the optical system. This allows capturing the polarization-based TM without requiring direct polarization measurement, making the network to get deeper understanding of light scattering and enabling the creation of an accurate digital twin that can be employed for inverse problems, such as image transmission.

Our approach diverges from traditional deep learning models, which often lack transparency and operate as black box systems. These conventional models typically rely heavily on the data's features, limiting their generalizability and constraining them to their training datasets. In contrast, our method demonstrates the high precision with which transmission matrices can be extracted. These matrices enable not only the forward transmission of information from SLM pattern to speckle but also the precise reconstruction of the SLM pattern from a given speckle pattern, facilitated by the ability to compute gradients through the digital twin and a regularization technique.

Consequently, our method offers a fully interpretable framework relevant to a range of light scattering applications, opening new opportunities for significant advancements in the field. Additionally, this approach is valuable for applications in physics-based neural networks where the system's gradient is required, contributing to the pathway toward optical and photonics-based AI.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Mohammadrahim Kazemzadeh: conceptualization (lead); formal analysis (lead); investigation (lead); methodology (lead); software (lead); validation (lead); visualization (lead); writing—original draft (lead); writing—review & editing (lead). **Liam Collard:** methodology (equal). **Linda Piscopo:** methodology (equal). **Massimo De Vittorio:** supervision (equal). **Ferruccio Pisanello:** supervision (lead).

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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- [1] I. M. Vellekoop, A. Mosk, *Opt. Lett.* **2007**, *32*, 2309.
- [2] R. Di Leonardo, S. Bianchi, *Opt. Express* **2011**, *19*, 247.
- [3] I. N. Papadopoulos, S. Farahi, C. Moser, D. Psaltis, *Opt. Express* **2012**, *20*, 10583.
- [4] M. C. Velsink, Z. P. Lyu, P. W. H. Pinkse, L. V. Amitonova, *Opt. Express* **2021**, *29*, 6523.

- [5] S. H. Li, C. Saunders, D. J. Lum, J. Murray-Bruce, V. K. Goyal, T. Cizmar, D. B. Phillips, *Light: Sci. Appl.* **2021**, *10*, 88.
- [6] T. Čižmár, K. Dholakia, *Opt. Express* **2011**, *19*, 18871.
- [7] L. Collard, F. Pisano, M. Pisanello, A. Balena, M. De Vittorio, F. Pisanello, *APL Photonics* **2021**, *6*, 051301.
- [8] L. Collard, F. Pisano, D. Zheng, A. Balena, M. F. Kashif, M. Pisanello, A. D'Orazio, L. M. de la Prida, C. Ciraci, M. Grande, M. De Vittorio, F. Pisanello, *Small* **2022**, *18*, 2200975.
- [9] M. N'Gom, T. B. Norris, E. Michielssen, R. R. Nadakuditi, *Opt. Lett.* **2018**, *43*, 419.
- [10] L. Collard, M. Kazemzadeh, M. De Vittorio, F. Pisanello, *Opt. Express* **2024**, *32*, 39661.
- [11] L. Piscopo, L. Collard, F. Pisano, A. Balena, M. D. Vittorio, F. Pisanello, *Opt. Express* **2024**, *32*, 24144.
- [12] S. Turtaev, I. T. Leite, T. Altwegg-Boussac, J. M. Pakan, N. L. Rochefort, T. Čižmár, *Light: Sci. Appl.* **2018**, *7*, 92.
- [13] Z. Wen, Z. Dong, Q. Deng, C. Pang, C. F. Kaminski, X. Xu, H. Yan, L. Wang, S. Liu, J. Tang, W. Chen, X. Liu, Q. Yang, *Nat. Photonics* **2023**, *17*, 679.
- [14] E. Cuhe, P. Marquet, C. Depeursinge, *Appl. Opt.* **2000**, *39*, 4070.
- [15] M. Plöschner, T. Tyc, T. Čižmár, *Nat. Photonics* **2015**, *9*, 529.
- [16] S. M. Popoff, G. Lerosey, R. Carminati, M. Fink, A. C. Boccard, S. Gigan, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2010**, *104*, 100601.
- [17] L. Collard, L. Piscopo, F. Pisano, D. Zheng, M. De Vittorio, F. Pisanello, *PLoS One* **2023**, *18*, e0290300.
- [18] P. Ják, M. Šiler, J. Ježek, A. Cifuentes, J. Trägårdh, P. Zemánek, T. Čižmár, *Photonics* **2022**, *9*, 37.
- [19] N. Borhani, E. Kakkava, C. Moser, D. Psaltis, *Optica* **2018**, *5*, 960.
- [20] B. Rahmani, D. Loterie, E. Kakkava, N. Borhani, U. Teğin, D. Psaltis, C. Moser, *Nat. Mach. Intell.* **2020**, *2*, 403.
- [21] P. Caramazza, O. Moran, R. Murray-Smith, D. Faccio, *Nat. Commun.* **2019**, *10*, 2029.
- [22] C. Zhu, E. A. Chan, Y. Wang, W. Peng, R. Guo, B. Zhang, C. Soci, Y. Chong, *Sci. Rep.* **2021**, *11*, 896.
- [23] R. Xu, L. Zhang, Z. Chen, Z. Wang, D. Zhang, *Laser Photonics Rev.* **2023**, *17*, 2200339.
- [24] B. Rahmani, D. Loterie, G. Konstantinou, D. Psaltis, C. Moser, *Light: Sci. Appl.* **2018**, *7*, 69.
- [25] M. Kazemzadeh, L. Collard, F. Pisano, L. Piscopo, C. Ciraci, M. De Vittorio, F. Pisanello, *Opt. Express* **2024**, *32*, 26414.
- [26] L. Collard, M. Kazemzadeh, L. Piscopo, M. De Vittorio, F. Pisanello, *Opt. Express* **2024**, *32*, 18896.
- [27] G. Wu, Y. Sun, L. Yin, Z. Song, W. Yu, *Opt. Lett.* **2023**, *48*, 2764.
- [28] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, L. Kaiser, I. Polosukhin, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, Neural Information Processing Systems Foundation, Inc., Long Beach, California, USA **2017**, Vol. 30.
- [29] Y. Chen, B. Song, J. Wu, W. Lin, W. Huang, *Appl. Opt.* **2023**, *62*, 266.
- [30] Z. Liu, Y. Lin, Y. Cao, H. Hu, Y. Wei, Z. Zhang, S. Lin, B. Guo, in *Proc. of the IEEE/CVF Int. Conf. on Computer Vision* **2021**, pp. 10012–10022.
- [31] S. Goel, C. Conti, S. Leedumrongwatthanakun, M. Malik, *Opt. Express* **2023**, *31*, 32824.
- [32] L. G. Wright, T. Onodera, M. M. Stein, T. Wang, D. T. Schachter, Z. Hu, P. L. McMahon, *Nature* **2022**, *601*, 549.
- [33] U. Teğin, M. Yldrm, I. Oğuz, C. Moser, D. Psaltis, *Nat. Comput. Sci.* **2021**, *1*, 542.
- [34] I. Oğuz, J. Ke, Q. Weng, F. Yang, M. Yildirim, N. U. Dinc, J.-L. Hsieh, C. Moser, D. Psaltis, *Opt. Lett.* **2023**, *48*, 5249.
- [35] Z. Liu, P. Luo, X. Wang, X. Tang, in *Proc. of Int. Conf. on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, CentroParque Convention Center in Santiago, Chile **2015**.